

A quantitative equilibrium studies on mixed ligand complexes of cadmium with nitrogen, oxygen and sulphur containing drugs and amino acids

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Abstract : A quantitative equilibrium studies on metal-ligand equilibria involving cadmium ion with drugs, (2S)-1-(3-mercapto-2-methyl propionyl)-L-proline i.e. captopril and 4-[2-hydroxy-3-(1-methyl ethyl amino)propoxy] benzene acetamide i.e. atenolol with glycine and serine in 50% (v/v) alcohol-water mixture at 30 ± 0.1 °C and ionic strength of 0.1 M NaClO₄ has been made. Formation of complex species have been evaluated by computer program and discussed by Irving-Rossotti technique.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complex, cadmium, amino acids.

The affinity of metals towards sulphur containing ligand was attributed towards increase in polarization of sulphur atom and reduced steric hinderance¹. Interesting results have been reported earlier on complex formation reactions on oxygen, nitrogen and oxygen-nitrogen mixed donor ligands². The metal complexes of Cu^{II}, Cd^{II} and Ni^{II} with sulphur containing ligand showed by IR spectra that the co-ordination takes place through both sulphur and oxygen atoms as potential donors³. It has been shown that the stability of transition metal complexes decreases as the group changes from -SH to -OH to -NH₂⁴. Expecting some useful information on mixed ligand complexes of such ligands a detailed pH metric study involving captopril and atenolol with cadmium metal has been made and the results are discussed.

Results and discussion

Binary complexes : By following Irving-Rossotti technique the protonation constants K_1^H and K_2^H of drugs (captopril, atenolol), amino acids (glycine and serine) and their stepwise metal-ligand formation constants (K_{ML}^H and $K_{ML_2}^{ML}$) have been determined (Table 1) for the purpose of comparison with those of the ternary systems. From the titration, complete formation of MR (charges are omitted for the sake of simplicity) is found to occur at lower pH and they are stable at higher pH. The complexing tendency of cadmium metal is found to be more with captopril than atenolol.

In captopril the higher equilibrium constant of metal ligand

interaction is because the sulphur containing donor captopril binds the metal through mercapto group. The amide group present near the carboxylic group is having a tendency of electron withdrawal by mesomeric effect and also there is partial steric hinderance associated with mercapto group. In atenolol the lower value of metal ligand interaction is because no considerable inductive or field effect is operative. The hydroxyl group present in the structure is alcoholic and the second metal ligand complex formation takes place at much higher pH, which cannot be determined by this technique. Hence, only one value of metal ligand interaction is observed. The amino group present in the structure is so neutral that it cannot dissociate.

Mixed ligand complexes : The stability of mixed ligand complexes is mainly governed by the characteristics of the approaching secondary ligand. The stability therefore depends mainly on the ring size which affects the overall basicity of the secondary ligand. It can be inferred that the stability of complex depends more on the length and spatial configuration of the chelate ring than on the acidity of the complexing agent. At the pH of secondary ligand combination, the formation of mixed ligand can be represented by equilibria (1) and (2).

(charges are omitted for simplicity)

Only 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes have been used in this study to ensure the exclusive formation of the simplest ternary complex MRL. Considering the pK values of the ligands and hydrolytic constants of M²⁺ ions the following species have been considered to exist in the complexation equilibria. M²⁺, RH², RH, R²⁻, M(OH)₂, MR(OH), MR, L²⁺, ML(OH), L²⁻ and MRL(OH).

The relative stabilities of mixed ligand complexes can be quantitatively expressed in terms of Δ log K, K_r, K_R and K_L values which are defined by equations.

$$\Delta \log K = \log \beta_{111} - \log_{10} - \log_{01} \quad (3)$$

$$K_r = \beta_{111}^2 / \beta_{20} \beta_{02} \quad (4)$$

$$K_R = \beta_{111} / \log K_{10} \quad (5)$$

$$K_L = \beta_{111} / \log K_{01} \quad (6)$$

The drug captopril (R₁) and glycine (L₁) both form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with Cd^{II}. The species distribution curves (Fig. 1) of CdR₁L₁ indicate the formation of ternary complex to about 71% at pH 4.3 and is constant throughout the pH range which is shown by parallel line to X-axis. It can also be observed that the formation of binary species is 30% at pH 4.3 and remains constant, the concentration of HR is very low 1.7% initially at pH 4.3 and reduces to zero with increase in pH. The constant value of the concentration of ternary species during the entire pH range shown by percentage distribution curve of CdRL species indicates that the formation of ternary complex takes place by reaction

Table 1. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants in binary system

Ligands	K ₁ ^H	K ₂ ^H	log K _{ML} ^M	log K _{ML₂} ^{ML}
Captopril	3.85	10.68	10.03	7.96
Atenolol	9.00	-	-	3.10
Glycine	3.10	9.63	4.21	5.44
Serine	3.25	9.20	3.33	4.59

The comparison of β₁₁₁ values with β₂₀ and β₀₂ of these system reveals the preferential formation of ternary complexes over binary ones. The low values of K_R and K_L show more stability of ternary complexes with respect to binary complexes of primary and secondary ligands. The positive values of K_r also confirms the stability of mixed ligand complexes. The negative value of Δ log K reveals that the stability of mixed ligand complex is comparable with 1 : 2 complex of binary species. The 1 : 2 complex is less stable than the stability of 1 : 1

complex. Hence, the stability of mixed ligand is less than stability of 1 : 1 complex. Hence, negative values of Δ log K.

In CdR₂L₁ system (Fig. 2), the primary ligand forms 1 : 1 complexes and the secondary ligand forms 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with Cd^{II}. It has been observed that the stability of mixed ligand complexes of captopril are found to be higher than the mixed ligand complexes of atenolol which is shown in Table 2. The positive values of K_R, K_L and K_r show the stability of mixed ligand complexes but these complexes are less stable than the 1 : 1 complexes of binary ones hence we get negative values of Δ log K.

Table 2. Stability constants of ternary complexes

R	L	β ₁₁₁	β ₂₀	β ₀₂	K _R	K _L	K _r	Δ log K
Captopril	Glycine	13.71	17.99	9.65	3.86	8.27	0.99	-2.40
	Serine	13.52	17.99	7.92	3.59	9.03	1.05	-1.64
Atenolol	Glycine	7.29	3.10	9.65	4.19	1.85	1.14	-1.25
	Serine	7.69	3.10	7.92	4.59	3.10	1.39	0.02

The species distribution diagram reveals the preferential formation of ternary species over binary species of primary and secondary ligands. The species R, which is 100% initially, goes on sharply decreasing to about 10% at pH 9.9. The concentration of CdR increases to 4.5% at pH 9.9 and also the concentration of binary species CdL which is 96% at pH 6.3 slowly decreases to 84%. From these observations it is clear that R is used in the formation of CdRL with increasing pH. The percentage formation of mixed ligand complex is very less i.e. 9%. The decrease in R to such a large extent may be due to its use in formation of CdR, which also increases with pH and some other species, which cannot be detected by this method.

In Fig. 3, the CdR₁L₂ system, it is observed that the primary ligand R₁ and secondary ligand L₂ form both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with Cd^{II}. The positive values of K_R and K_L confirms the stability of ternary complexes. The low values of K_r also indicate low stability of ternary complexes. The

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

negative value of $\Delta \log K$ of these complexes is compared with the 1 : 2 complex which is less stable than 1 : 1 complex in binary species.

The species distribution curve shows similar behaviour to CdR_1L_1 system. The concentration of ternary complex starts from about 70% from pH 4.5 and remains constant, which is shown by straight line parallel to X-axis. The percentage of CdR_2 is 31% at pH 4.5 and remains constant till pH 7.6, which is also shown by straight parallel line to X-axis. The concentration of HL is negligible i.e. 1.6% at pH 4.5 and approaches to zero at pH 6.0. From these two curves it is obvious that the formation of ternary complex is favoured by reaction.

which is similar to CdR_1L_1 system.

In CdR_2L_2 system (Fig. 4) the primary ligand R_2 forms 1 : 1 complex and secondary ligand forms 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with Cd^{II} . The stability of mixed ligand complexes of serine as secondary ligand is less as compared to CdR_1L_2 system. The positive values of $\Delta \log K$ indicate stability of ternary complex over binary species.

The species distribution curve points to the fact that the formation of ternary complex is preferred over binary species CdR . The concentration of R is 99% at pH 6.5 initially which decreases rapidly to 5.3 at pH 9.9. Similarly the concentration of CdL , which is 89%, decreases to 43% at pH 9.9. The concentration of CdR increases slowly to 5.6% at pH 9.9. The ternary complex concentration is zero initially which gradually increases to 46% at pH 9.9 which confirms the ternary complex formation by reaction involving L and CdR species. The stability of binary species MR, ML and ternary species MRL complexes is in the expected order. The stability constants of ternary complexes were found to be greater in R_1 than in R_2 . The higher stability of R_1 chelate may be due to the extra stabilization of five membered ring and also because it is a sulphha drug. The low stabilization of R_2 complexes may be due to its only one dissociation constant.

Fig. 3

Trends in $\log \beta_{111}$ values were found to be same as that of $\log K_{MRL}^M$ values. The $\Delta \log K_{MRL}^M$ values were less negative or positive. This may be attributed to the π -acidic character of drugs and O-N coordination of amino acids.

Fig. 4

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade and all the solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water and standardized by usual procedures⁵. The titrations were carried out using a digital pH meter [Elico model LI-120] in conjunction with combined electrode. All titrations were carried out at 30 ± 0.1 °C. For the determination of formation constants of ternary complexes, following solutions were prepared, 0.008 M perchloric acid, 0.002 M primary ligands (drugs), 0.002 M secondary ligands (amino acids), 0.002 M metal solutions at an ionic strength of 0.1 M sodium perchlorate. The titrations were plotted by using experimental data, which were utilized to analyze the proton ligand formation constants of primary and secondary ligands and their metal complexes. Concentration of total metal ions, total ligands, free metal, free ligands and various possible species that are formed during the complexation are calculated using SCOGS program⁶. Complex formation equilibria were elucidated with the aid of the species distribution curves obtained as computer output⁷.

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References

1. O. Prochazkova, J. Podlahova and J. Podlaha Colin, *Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1973, **38**, 1120; P. Petras, J. Podlahova and J. Podlaha Colin, *Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1973, **38**, 3321; S. E. Livingston, *Quart. Rev.*, 1965, **19**, 388.
2. D. D. Perrin, "Stability Constants of Metal Ion Complexes", Pergamon, New York, 1979; J. Springborg and I. Stofte, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1997, **51**, 357; K. Varnagy, J. Szabo, I. Sovago, G. Malandrinis, N. Hadjiliadisi, Sanna and G. Micera, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2000, 467; S. Brooker, T. C. Davidson, S. J. Hay, R. J. Kelley, D. K. Kennepohl, P. G. Plieger, B. Mubarak, K. S. Murray, E. Bill and E. Bothe, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2001, **3**, 216; K. Oaz, K. Varnagy, J. Sovago, L. Lennert, H. Suli Varga, D. Sanna and G. Micera, *New J. Chem.*, 2001, **25**, 7001; D. Sanna, C. G. Agoston, I. Sovago and G. Micera, *Polyhedron*, 2001, **20**, 937; M. Singh and R. Nayan, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1996, **8**, 470.
3. A. Kumar, S. Jain and S. K. Tiwari, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 2439.
4. C. Furlani, M. L. Luciaii and R. Chandari, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 3121.
5. G. A. Nelson, M. P. Crawford and B. J. Geddes, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 1123.
6. I. G. Sayce, *Talanta*, 1988, **15**, 1397.
7. R. Nayan and A. K. Dey, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 892.